

Digital Revolution In Orthodontic Impressions

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Abstract

Intraoral scanners (IOSs) have transformed modern orthodontics by replacing conventional impression techniques with digital workflows. They improve patient comfort, increase clinical efficiency, eliminate the need for physical casts, and enhance communication through CAD/CAM integration. This review discusses the history, scanning technologies, advantages, limitations, and commonly used intraoral scanners such as iTero, TRIOS 3, CEREC Omnicam, and True Definition. Although IOSs have certain limitations, including high costs and learning curves, they continue to play a major role in the advancement of digital orthodontics.

Keywords: Intra oral scanners, Technology, Digital Workflow.

Introduction

Orthodontics has entered a rapidly evolving digital era in which technological advancements have significantly transformed everyday clinical practice. Modern innovations have reduced dependence on traditional materials and methods such as paper records, radiographic exposure, and physical dental casts. Among these developments, digital intraoral scanners (IOSs) have become an integral component of contemporary orthodontic workflows. Their introduction has streamlined conventional laboratory procedures, minimized inaccuracies associated with cast fabrication, and eliminated many of the challenges related to the storage and maintenance of physical models. Consequently, IOS technology has expanded the scope of in-office clinical applications and improved overall efficiency in orthodontic care.¹

History

- The introduction of intraoral digital scanners has significantly transformed orthodontic practice, replacing traditional alginate and polyvinyl siloxane (PVS) impression techniques with more advanced digital methods.
- Dr. François Duret of France was the first to introduce the concept of computer aided design and computer aided manufacturing (CAD/CAM) in dentistry in 1973.
- A major milestone in digital dentistry occurred in 1987 when Sirona Dental Systems introduced the prototype Chair-side Economical Restoration of Aesthetic

Ceramics (CEREC®) system for restorative procedures.

- The CEREC system became a pioneering innovation in CAD/CAM dentistry and laid the foundation for the development of digital impression technologies, despite the early limitations in scanning and milling accuracy.
- For many years, CEREC remained the dominant system in the field until the introduction of the Cadent iTero digital impression scanner in 2006.
- In 2008, iTero demonstrated the capability of performing complete full-arch intraoral scans, representing a significant advancement in digital impression technology.
- Align Technology acquired Cadent in 2011, after which iTero scanning systems were integrated into the digital workflow for Invisalign treatment.
- Following these developments, numerous dental manufacturers began investing heavily in intraoral scanner technology to improve scanning efficiency, precision, and clinical applications.
- By the 2017 International Dental Show in Cologne, more than fourteen intraoral scanning systems had been showcased, highlighting the rapid expansion of the digital dentistry market. In 2012, 3M ESPE introduced the True Definition

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scanner for digital submission of cases involving Incognito custom lingual appliances.

- Ormco later introduced the Lythos digital impression system, which supported Insignia and Clearguide orthodontic appliance systems.
- Increased compatibility among manufacturers further expanded the clinical utility of intraoral scanners, allowing digital scans from different systems to be used across multiple orthodontic platforms.²

Advantages of Digital Scanning

- Reduced patient discomfort and improved patient acceptance
- Greater time efficiency compared to conventional impression methods
- Elimination of plaster casts and physical model storage
- Improved communication with dental technicians through digital data transfer
- Enhanced communication and visualization with patients
- Easier storage, retrieval, and sharing of digital records
- Better integration with CAD/CAM and digital orthodontic workflows
- Increased efficiency in appliance fabrication and treatment planning.³

Disadvantages of Digital Scanning

- Difficulty in accurately recording deep marginal lines of prepared teeth
- Presence of a learning curve requiring operator training and experience
- High initial purchase and maintenance costs
- Limited accuracy in certain complex clinical situations
- Dependence on software systems and digital infrastructure
- Technique sensitivity, especially in moisture control and restricted intraoral areas
- Possibility of scanning errors in reflective or subgingival regions
- Rapid technological advancements may lead to equipment obsolescence.³

Scanning Technology

- Digital intraoral scanners are classified as Class I medical electrical devices and are manufactured according to ANSI/IEC 60601-1 standards.
- Most intraoral scanning systems consist of three primary components:
 - A mobile workstation for data management
 - A computer interface for reviewing and approving scans
 - A handheld scanning wand used intraorally to capture digital impressions
- The scanning process involves projecting either laser light or structured white light onto the oral structures. The reflected light is then captured by sensors or cameras within the scanner wand to generate a three-dimensional digital model.
- Advanced software algorithms analyze thousands of captured data points to create an accurate 3D representation of the dental arches and surrounding tissues.⁴

Types of Imaging Technologies Used in Intraoral Scanners

1. Triangulation Technology (Fig.1)

- Used in early systems such as CEREC scanners
- Operates by calculating distances and angles between the light source, sensor, and object surface

Based on geometric principles, including the Pythagorean theorem

Requires the application of an opaque powder coating to ensure uniform light reflection and accurate scanning.⁴

Figure 1- Triangulation technology

Kravitz ND, Groth C, Jones PE, Graham JW, Redmond WR. Intraoral digital scanners - Overview. JCO 2014; 48: 337-347.

2. Parallel Confocal Imaging (Fig. 2)

- Uses laser light projected through a filtering pinhole onto the target surface
- Captures only focused reflected light while eliminating out-of-focus information
- Produces highly accurate scans by collecting multiple optical slices of the object
- The collected slices are combined using a “point and stitch” reconstruction process to generate a complete 3D image.⁴

Figure 2- Parallel Confocal technology

Kravitz ND, Groth C, Jones PE, Graham JW, Redmond WR. Intraoral digital scanners - Overview. JCO 2014; 48: 337-347.

3. Accordion Fringe Interferometry (AFI) (Fig. 3)

- Utilizes multiple light patterns, known as fringe patterns, projected onto the tooth surfaces
- Distortion of these fringe patterns caused by surface curvature is recorded by a high definition camera
- The system analyzes these distortions to calculate precise three dimensional measurements
- Accuracy is less affected by variations in tooth color or restorative materials.⁴

Figure 3- Accordion Fringe Interferometry (AFI)

Kravitz ND, Groth C, Jones PE, Graham JW, Redmond WR. Intraoral digital scanners - Overview. JCO 2014; 48: 337-347.

4. Three Dimensional In Motion Video Imaging (Fig. 4)

- Employs high definition video cameras with trinocular imaging technology
- Captures continuous video sequences of the dentition in real time
- A complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) sensor converts light into electrical signals for processing
- Enables rapid acquisition of 3D data with improved efficiency compared to point and stitch systems
- Requires only minimal powder application compared to triangulation systems.⁴

Figure 4 - Three Dimensional In Motion Video Imaging

Kravitz ND, Groth C, Jones PE, Graham JW, Redmond WR. Intraoral digital scanners - Overview. JCO 2014; 48: 337-347.

Additional Considerations

- AFI and 3D in-motion video systems capture images in real time, making scanning faster and more efficient.
- AFI scanners possess a higher dynamic luminosity range, allowing reflective surfaces to be scanned without the need for powder coating.
- The choice of scanning technology influences the scanner's speed, resolution, precision, and overall clinical performance.⁴

Powdering in Digital Intraoral Scanning

- Certain intraoral scanners require the application of a thin contrast powder layer, commonly referred to as powdering, dusting, or accent frosting, before scanning.
- Powdering is necessary because translucent tooth structures and restorative materials scatter light irregularly, making it difficult for scanner algorithms to accurately interpret reflected signals.
- The contrast powder is usually composed of:
 - Titanium dioxide
 - Zirconium oxide (less commonly used)
 - Amorphous silica
 - Aluminum hydroxide
- The powder is applied using a handheld spray dispenser that distributes a fine, uniform coating over the surfaces to be scanned.⁴

iTero Element Align Technology

- The iTero scanner is considered one of the pioneering and most widely recognized intraoral scanning systems in digital orthodontics.
- Its popularity increased significantly after Align Technology acquired Cadent, primarily because of its integration with the Invisalign® system. (Fig. 5)

- By the end of 2017, more than five million Invisalign cases had reportedly been treated, contributing to the widespread adoption of iTero scanners among orthodontic practitioners.¹

Features of iTero Element

The newer iTero Element scanner provides:

- Real-time treatment outcome simulation through the Simulator feature
- Monitoring of Invisalign treatment progress using Progress Assessment
- Open source STL file export for compatibility with different digital systems
- Enhanced communication and digital workflow integration

Scanning Technology

- Utilizes parallel confocal imaging technology for data acquisition
- Operates without the need for powder coating, making the scanning process more comfortable and convenient.⁵

Figure 5 – iTero Intraoral scanner

Hwang HH, Chou CW, Chen YJ, Yao CCJ. An overview of digital intraoral scanners: past, present and future from an orthodontic perspective. Taiwan J Orthod. 2018; 30 (3): 81-92.

TRIOS 3 / TRIOS 3 Wireless - 3 Shape

- 3 Shape, established in 2000, is a rapidly expanding company known for developing both intraoral scanners and laboratory based extraoral scanners for digital dentistry.
- The first TRIOS scanner was introduced in 2010, while the advanced TRIOS 3 system was launched in 2015 with major technological improvements.

Key Features of TRIOS 3

- Improved defogging efficiency allows scanning to begin immediately after startup
- The scanner tip is automatically preheated, eliminating the waiting time previously required for lens warming
- The scanning wand is significantly smaller and more ergonomic than earlier versions
- Unlike some systems that use disposable sleeves, the TRIOS scanner sleeve is autoclavable, supporting effective infection control and reusability.⁶

Scanning Technology

- Uses Ultrafast Optical Sectioning technology based on the confocal laser principle

- The confocal plane changes continuously during scanning, reducing the need for maintaining a fixed distance between the scanner and the tooth surface
- This design improves scanning convenience and workflow efficiency

TRIOS 3 Wireless

- Introduced at the 2017 International Dental Show as the world's first wireless intraoral scanner (Fig. 6)
- Eliminates the traditional cable connection between the scanner wand and computer unit
- Provides greater flexibility, easier handling, and a less restrictive scanning experience for clinicians.¹

Figure 6 – TRIOS 3 Wireless Intraoral scanner

Hwang HH, Chou CW, Chen YJ, Yao CCJ. An overview of digital intraoral scanners: past, present and future from an orthodontic perspective. *Taiwan J Orthod.* 2018; 30 (3): 81-92.

CEREC Omnicam Sirona Dentsply

- The CEREC system is one of the earliest and most established CAD/CAM systems in digital dentistry.
- CEREC Omnicam represents an advanced generation of the CEREC system and differs significantly from the earlier Bluecam model.

Scanning Technology

- Based on the triangulation imaging principle
- Utilizes continuous video streaming technology instead of combining multiple static images
- Enables smoother and more efficient digital scanning procedures

Powder Free Scanning

- Unlike earlier CEREC systems, Omnicam does not require powder application before scanning
- This improves patient comfort and simplifies the clinical workflow.¹

True Definition - 3M

- The True Definition scanner by 3M was developed as an advancement of the earlier Lava C.O.S. scanning system.
- In 2016, 3M introduced the Mobile True Definition scanner, a portable version that retained the same hardware and software capabilities as the original system.

Key Features

- Demonstrated high scanning accuracy in several comparative studies
- Features one of the smallest and lightest scanner wands available, comparable in size and weight to a conventional dental handpiece
- The compact design improves operator comfort and intraoral accessibility

Powder Requirement

- A thin layer of contrast powder is recommended to achieve optimal scanning accuracy
- Many clinicians consider the brief powdering process acceptable because it enhances scan precision and image quality

Limitations

- Does not provide real-time full color digital scans, unlike some newer intraoral scanning systems

Software and Compatibility

- 3M primarily emphasizes hardware development rather than proprietary software systems
- The scanner supports multiple orthodontic and restorative digital platforms through open-source communication systems such as:
 - Incognito
 - Invisalign
 - SureSmile
 - ClearCorrect¹

Conclusion

Intraoral scanners have become an important part of contemporary orthodontic practice due to their accuracy, efficiency, and patient friendly nature. They simplify clinical procedures and support advanced digital treatment planning and appliance fabrication. Despite some limitations, continuous technological developments are expected to further expand their applications and improve orthodontic care in the future.

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